

Growth Performance of Different Varieties of Grapes in Karnataka

Sathyendra Kumar A.D.^{1}, Satish Chandra Pant², K.C. Gummagolmath¹, and Mahesh Mahadeo Kadam³*

¹National Institute of Agricultural Extension Management (MANAGE), Hyderabad-500030 (Telangana) and ²Doon Business School, Dehradun-248001 (Uttarakhand) and ³CCS National Institute of Agricultural Marketing (CCS NIAM), Jaipur-302033 (Rajasthan)

*Corresponding author's email: sathyendra.prakrit@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The study throws light on the growth performance of different varieties of grape cultivation in the state of Karnataka across its districts and divisions. The state produces majorly four varieties of grapes, namely Bengaluru Blue, Anab-e-Shahi, seedless varieties and miscellaneous varieties. The area and production of all varieties of grapes observed positive and significant growth during the study period. The results revealed that the growth was positively significant in the area (7.23 per cent per annum), production (7.96 per cent per annum) and productivity (0.67 per cent per annum). The growth rate was highest in the case of the Belagavi division, followed by the Kalaburagi division. The highest rate of increase in the area and productivity of grapes was recorded in the case of the Chikkaballapura district. The values of instability indices for the area (6.73), production (13.72) and productivity (7.49) were comparatively lower, indicating their stability in the state. Further, the instability analysis indicated that the area and productivity of grapes in the Mysuru division were more unstable than in other state divisions.

Keywords

Area, compound growth rate, instability index, production, productivity.

JEL Codes

Q10, Q11, Q16.

INTRODUCTION

Grapes occupied the sixth position among all fruits in India in production, accounting for only 3.10 per cent of total fruit production in 2018-19, placed next to banana, mango, citrus fruits, papaya and guava. The current area under grape cultivation in India is estimated to be 1.40 lakh hectares, with an annual production of 30.41 lakh tons (Department of Agriculture and Farmer Welfare, 2018). While 78 per cent of grape is used for table purposes, approximately 20 per cent is dried for raisin production and 2 per cent is used in the production of juice and wine, etc. (Sharma & Adsule, 2007; Chadha, 2018). Only a few states in India produce grapes. Maharashtra, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh are the major states for grape production, accounting for 98 per cent of

the total production. States like Haryana, Madhya Pradesh, Mizoram and Jammu & Kashmir also contribute a meagre proposition to the total production of grapes in the country (Department of Agriculture and Farmer Welfare, 2018)

Karnataka is India's second-largest producer of grapes in the country, next to Maharashtra. The state cultivates different varieties of grapes. The state's prominent grape-growing regions are Nandi Valley, Cauvery Valley, and Krishna Valley (Nadoni, Uma, & Gangannavar, 2018). The agro-ecological condition of the state is also advantageous for grape farming. The state has numerous vineyards and enjoys a healthy production of high-quality grapes every year. During 2018-19, the area under grape cultivation was 29.19 thousand hectares, accounting for

21 per cent of the country's total area under grape cultivation. Production was around 642.33 thousand tonnes, with productivity of 25.33 tonnes per hectare, which accounted for 21.12 per cent of the total production of grapes in India and the per hectare yield was 25.33 tons. Different varieties of grapes are cultivated in the state. The table varieties are Anab-e-Shahi, Bangalore Blue, Beauty Seedless, Bhokri (Pachadrakshi), Cheema Sahebi, Delight, and Gulabi (Panneer Drakshi, Muscat Hamburg), Himrod, Kali Sahebi, Kandhari, Khalili, Pandari Sahebi, Perlette, Selection 94, Pusa Seedless and Thompson Seedless. The raisin varieties are Thompson Seedless and Arkavati, and the wine varieties are Bangalore Blue, Thompson Seedless and Arka Kanchan, Cabernet, Shiraz, Zinfandal and Chenin blanc.

The progressive grape growers from the northern part of the state grow high-quality grapes and export their products to Europe, Russia, and Middle East countries (Sheikh et al., 2014). Considering the importance of grape production in Karnataka, the present study was conducted to compute district- and division-wise growth rate and instability indices of area, production and productivity of different varieties of grapes.

METHODOLOGY

The district-wise time series data on area, production and productivity of different varieties of grapes in Karnataka for the period from 2001-02 to 2018-19 were collected from various sources such as annual government reports NHB publications from 2001-02 to 2018-19 and Horticultural Statistics at a Glance 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018 published by Horticulture Statistics Division, Department of Agriculture, Cooperation and Farmers Welfare, Government of India, Horticulture Statistics of Karnataka State at a Glance published by Directorate of Horticulture, Government of Karnataka and data on Principle Crops in Karnataka published by Directorate of Economics and Statistics [DES], Government of Karnataka. The exponential function model was used to compute the annual compound growth rates in the area, production and productivity.

Instability Analysis

To study the variability in area and production of grapes, an index of instability was developed as a measure of variability. The coefficient of variation (CV) was calculated:

$$\text{Coefficient of variation (CV)} = \frac{\text{Standard deviation}}{\text{Mean}} \times 100$$

The formula suggested by Cuddy and Della in 1978

was used to compute the index of instability.

$$\text{Index of Instability} = \frac{\text{Standard deviation}}{\text{Mean}} \times 100 \times \sqrt{1-R^2}$$

The coefficient of variation was multiplied by the square root of the difference between the unity and coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2) in the cases where R^2 was significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of district-wise compound growth rate as well as instability indices of area, production and productivity of total grapes and different varieties of grapes, namely, Bengaluru Blue, Anab-e-Shahi, seedless varieties and miscellaneous varieties, were computed.

Total Grape Cultivation

The compound growth of the area, production and productivity as well as instability indices of grapes, are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The compound annual growth rates (CGRs) and instability index (I.I.) of individual varieties of grapes are presented in Tables 3 to 6.

The acreage under grape cultivation and production increased throughout the state at the rate of 7.23 and 7.96 per cent per annum, respectively, during 2001-02 to 2018-19. These results conform with the findings of Kumar and Devaraj (2018), who reported high growth in grape cultivation in Karnataka during 2001-02 to 2015-16, and Mokashi and Hosamani (2014), who analyzed the growth of grape production in Karnataka during 1985-86 to 2011-12 and, division-wise, the rate in area (9.05 per cent per annum), production (10.81 per cent per annum) and productivity (1.74 per cent per annum) was observed the highest in the case of the Belagavi division, followed by the Kalaburagi division. Many districts in the state registered a 1 per cent level of significant growth, which was reflected by lower productivity growth in the state (0.67 per cent per annum) and all the four administrative divisions of the state. The highest growth rate in the grapes' area, production, and productivity was observed in the Chikkaballapura district. Most of the districts registered positive growth rates in areas under grapes, and the results were significant at a 1 per cent level of probability. Only Bengaluru Urban and Kolar districts registered negative growth. A similar trend was observed with respect to production. However, the growth rates of productivity was found to be negative in the case of Koppal (-2.57 per cent per annum), Bengaluru Rural (-2.02 per cent per annum), Belagavi (-0.34 per cent per annum) and Bengaluru Urban (-0.23 per cent per annum) (Suvagiya et al., 2017).

The division wise analysis revealed that growth in the area was positive for all the regions, and it was highly

significant (4.76 per cent per annum) at a 5 per cent level of probability with respect to the Mysuru division. On the contrary, due to negative growth in yield, except Belagavi division, the growth rate in production was lower than growth in the area (Table 1).

The instability indices for the area, production and productivity of grapes in Karnataka are presented in Table 2. The instability indices of area (6.73), production (13.72) and yield (7.49) were lower, indicating their stability in the state. The area and production of grapes in the Mysuru division showed more instability than in other state divisions. The instability index was highest (60.85 per cent per annum) in the case of the Kolar district, followed by Chikkaballapura (40.05 per cent per annum) and Kalaburagi (39.82 per cent per annum). This resulted in a higher instability index in the case of the Mysuru division (46.11 per cent per annum). A similar trend was noticed in the instability index for production. However, the instability indices were comparatively low in the case of yield except in Chikkaballapura (38.07 per cent per annum) once again, the Mysuru division exhibited higher instability index with respect to yield.

Individual Variety of Grapes

Bengaluru Blue

Bengaluru Blue is closely connected to the American Concord variety, which has a strong natural resistance

against the insect disease called phylloxera bugs and foxy aroma and soft skin. It is known to have anti-cancer and anti-ageing properties. Grape is mainly used for raw consumption, or for making jams and jellies, juice and juice concentrates, or fortified wines (Subramanya, 2011). Karnataka received a geographical indication tag in 2013 for Bengaluru Blue from the Government of India.

The area and production of Bengaluru Blue grapes increased at 2.75 and 2.39 per cent per annum, respectively, in Karnataka during 2001–02 to 2018-19 (Table 3). Kumar and Devaraj (2016) has also observed that the area and production of Bengaluru Blue grapes increased at the rate of 5.15 and 4.29 per cent per annum, respectively, in the state during 2000–01 to 2014–15. The district-wise analysis revealed an increase in Bengaluru Blue grapes yield was found in the Chikkaballapura district (24.99 per cent per annum) only. While the growth in area and production was positive in the case of Bengaluru rural and other districts. There was a significant decline in yield in the Bengaluru Rural district. All other districts saw negative growth in the area, production and productivity. The highest stability of area (7.51), production (10.96), and productivity (5.10) were observed in Bengaluru rural. The overall state had lower instability in the area (9.74), production (11.84) and

Table 1. Compound growth rate for area, production and productivity of grapes in Karnataka, 2001-02 to 2018-19

Districts	Compound growth rates (per cent)		
	Area	Production	Productivity
Bengaluru Urban	-5.91***	-6.13***	-0.23*
Bengaluru Rural	3.80***	1.70***	-2.02***
Chikkaballapura	80.01***	128.62***	27.01***
Kolar	-15.71***	-16.23***	-0.61*
Bagalkote	9.14***	10.62***	1.36*
Belagavi	12.11***	11.72***	-0.34***
Vijayapura	8.46***	11.07***	2.40***
Kalaburagi	9.07***	11.80***	3.10***
Koppal	7.55***	4.60***	-2.75***
Other districts	12.00***	11.97***	2.52***
Karnataka	7.23***	7.96***	0.67***
Division			
Bengaluru	3.12***	3.03***	-0.03 ^{NS}
Belagavi	9.05***	10.81***	1.74***
Kalaburagi	10.21***	9.26***	-0.47 ^{NS}
Mysuru	4.76*	-0.27*	-4.45***

*** and * Significant at 1 and 10 per cent level.

NS: Non-significant.

productivity (5.30) during the study period. The instability index was relatively higher for the area (47.71 per cent per annum) and production (45.23 per cent per annum) in the case of the Kolar district.

Anab-e-Shahi

The Anab-e-Shahi variety is produced in Andhra Pradesh, Punjab, Haryana and Karnataka. It is widely adaptable to different agro-climatic conditions. This variety is late maturing but high yielding. Berries are elongated, medium-large, seeded and amber-coloured when fully ripe. The juice is clear and sweet, and fruits have a good keeping quality. It is mostly used for table purposes. It is highly susceptible to downy mildew. The

average yield of this variety is 35 tons per hectare (Sheikh et al., 2014). In Karnataka, more than 87 per cent of the Anab-e-Shahi grape is produced in the Chikkaballapura district, 11 per cent from Bengaluru urban and rural districts and only 1 per cent from other districts.

The acreage under Anab-e-Shahi cultivation increased at the rate of 1.96 per cent per annum and production at 3.45 per cent per annum in Karnataka during 2001-02 to 2018-19 (Table 4). Kumar and Devaraj (2016) reported that the area, production and productivity of Anab-e-Shahi in Karnataka increased at the rate of 2.52, 3.47, and 0.92 per cent per annum, respectively, during 2000-01 to 2014-15. The district-wise growth in area and production

Table 2. Instability indices for the area, production and productivity of grapes in Karnataka, 2001-02 to 2018-19

Districts	Instability Index		
	Area	Production	Productivity
Bengaluru urban	14.37	17.13	10.06
Bengaluru rural	5.67	6.50	5.04
Chikkaballapura	40.05	43.11	38.07
Kolar	60.85	74.74	9.33
Bagalkote	19.40	26.71	19.50
Belagavi	25.25	25.21	6.20
Vijayapura	14.51	30.35	14.27
Kalaburagi	39.82	28.00	13.13
Koppal	13.59	14.70	14.94
Other districts	29.32	29.42	16.41
Karnataka	6.73	13.72	7.49
Division			
Bengaluru	7.55	13.00	7.73
Belagavi	13.30	25.83	10.86
Kalaburagi	22.48	16.10	13.24
Mysuru	46.11	37.00	39.30

Table 3. Compound growth rates and instability index of area, production and productivity of Bengaluru Blue grapes in Karnataka, 2001-02 to 2018-19

District	Compound growth rate (Percent)			Instability Index		
	Area	Production	Productivity	Area	Production	Productivity
Bengaluru Urban	-4.06***	-4.13***	-0.07 ^{NS}	20.18***	24.26***	11.39***
Bengaluru Rural	4.18***	3.81***	-0.35*	7.51***	10.96***	5.10***
Chikkaballapura	62.75***	103.43***	24.99***	31.93***	28.31***	37.44***
Kolar	-4.82***	-5.88***	-1.11***	47.71***	45.23***	7.74***
Other districts	6.76*	6.53*	-0.21 ^{NS}	135.56***	128.78***	14.66***
Karnataka	2.75***	2.39***	-0.36*	9.74***	11.84***	5.30***

*** and * Significant at 1 and 10 per cent level.
NS: Non-significant.

was also negative in all Anab-e-Shahi cultivation districts, except for Chikkaballapura and other minor cultivation districts. However, the productivity growth was significant in the Chikkaballapura district and non-significant in the rest of the cultivation districts during the study period. The instability indices of area, production and productivity of Anab-e-Shahi ranged from 17.06 to 149.53, 17.86 to 117.39, and 5.3 to 39.38, respectively, indicating that the area and production remained less stable, which in turn was responsible for fluctuations in Anab-e-Shahi production. Very high fluctuations in prices affected the acreage of Anab-e-Shahi production. The lowest instability indices of area and production were observed in the case of Bengaluru Urban district and that for productivity in Bengaluru Rural district.

Seedless Variety of Grapes

The seedless variety is grown in Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Karnataka. It has wide adaptability with seedless, ellipsoidal-elongated, golden-

yellow berries with medium-thin skin. The juice is straw coloured and sweet. The variety has a good shelf life and mainly used for table purposes and raisin making (National Horticultural Board, 2012). The average yield is 20-25 tons per hectare. Thompson Seedless, Sonaka, Flame Seedless, Sharad Seedless, Crimson Seedless and Red Globe are mostly cultivated in Karnataka.

The cultivation of seedless varieties of grape increased at the rate of 9.02 per cent per annum along with significant production growth (10.35 per cent per annum) and productivity (1.22 per cent per annum) in Karnataka during 2001-02 to 2018-19 (Table 5). The instability indices of area, production and productivity of seedless grapes to the tune of 22.61, 31.47 and 9.35, respectively, in Karnataka, indicated its stability. Positive and significant growth in the area, production and productivity of seedless varieties of grapes in Karnataka were also observed by Kumar and Devaraj (2016). The highest growth in the area (34.93 per cent per annum),

Table 4. Compound growth rates and instability index of area, production and productivity of Anab-e-Shahi grapes in Karnataka, 2001-02 to 2018-19

District	Compound growth rate (Percent)			Instability Index		
	Area	Production	Productivity	Area	Production	Productivity
Bengaluru Urban	-21.84 ^{***}	-27.00 ^{**}	-6.60 ^{***}	17.06 ^{***}	17.86 ^{***}	23.24 ^{***}
Bengaluru Rural	-0.32 ^{NS}	-1.80 [*]	-1.49 ^{NS}	22.75 ^{***}	22.61 ^{***}	5.38 ^{***}
Chikkaballapura	71.85 ^{***}	120.34 ^{***}	28.22 ^{***}	56.88 ^{***}	56.46 ^{***}	39.38 ^{***}
Kolar	-30.54 ^{***}	-34.05 ^{***}	-5.05 ^{***}	83.80 ^{***}	101.25 ^{***}	28.34 ^{***}
Other districts	6.84 ^{***}	6.75 ^{***}	-0.09 ^{***}	149.53 ^{***}	117.39 ^{***}	36.02 ^{***}
Karnataka	1.96 [*]	3.45 ^{***}	1.46 ^{NS}	23.05 ^{***}	28.60 ^{***}	14.72 ^{***}

^{***} and ^{*} Significant at 1 and 10 per cent level.

NS: Non-significant.

Table 5. Compound growth rates and instability index of area, production and productivity of seedless grapes in Karnataka, 2001-02 to 2018-19

District	Compound growth rate (Percent)			Instability Index		
	Area	Production	Productivity	Area	Production	Productivity
Bengaluru Rural	15.01 ^{***}	11.74 ^{***}	-2.84 ^{***}	22.33 ^{***}	27.42 ^{***}	9.90 ^{***}
Bagalkote	34.93 ^{***}	48.70 ^{***}	10.21 ^{***}	21.77 ^{***}	29.27 ^{***}	31.22 ^{***}
Belagavi	12.22 ^{***}	11.84 ^{***}	-0.34 ^{***}	25.35 ^{***}	25.16 ^{***}	6.19 ^{***}
Vijayapura	1.60 ^{NS}	1.80 ^{NS}	0.20 ^{NS}	36.01 ^{***}	48.33 ^{***}	29.34 ^{***}
Bidar	8.04 ^{***}	3.37 ^{NS}	-4.32 ^{***}	44.05 ^{***}	66.85 ^{***}	26.27 ^{***}
Kalaburagi	17.74 ^{NS}	25.72 ^{***}	6.78 ^{***}	26.46 ^{***}	26.40 ^{***}	19.58 ^{***}
Koppal	7.80 ^{***}	4.26 ^{***}	-3.28 ^{***}	15.91 ^{***}	17.10 ^{***}	10.89 ^{***}
Other districts	21.33 ^{***}	23.83 ^{***}	2.06 ^{**}	37.96 ^{***}	33.05 ^{***}	18.65 ^{***}
Karnataka	9.02 ^{***}	10.35 ^{***}	1.22 ^{***}	22.61 ^{***}	31.47 ^{***}	9.35 ^{***}

^{***} and ^{**} Significant at 1 and 5 per cent level.

NS: Non-significant.

Table 6. Compound growth rates and instability index of area, production and productivity of miscellaneous varieties of grapes in Karnataka, 2001-02 to 2018-19

District	Compound growth rate (Percent)			Instability Index		
	Area	Production	Productivity	Area	Production	Productivity
Bagalkote	0.20 ^{NS}	1.18 ^{NS}	0.97 ^{NS}	116.25 ^{***}	123.37 ^{***}	48.45 ^{***}
Bengaluru Rural	1.96 ^{***}	-4.66 ^{***}	-6.50 ^{***}	9.18 ^{***}	23.63 ^{***}	24.36 ^{***}
Bengaluru Urban	-19.88 ^{***}	-26.17 ^{***}	-7.85 ^{NS}	163.69 ^{***}	226.92 ^{***}	65.98 ^{***}
Chikkaballapura	59.77 ^{***}	102.89 ^{***}	26.99 ^{***}	53.62 ^{***}	59.51 ^{***}	36.78 ^{***}
Kalaburagi	8.01 ^{NS}	20.93 [*]	11.96 ^{**}	112.57 ^{***}	112.61 ^{***}	39.55 ^{***}
Vijayapura	27.97 ^{***}	50.84 ^{***}	12.34 ^{**}	300.71 ^{***}	333.63 ^{***}	55.95 ^{***}
Other districts	-0.47 ^{NS}	-1.32 ^{NS}	-0.85 ^{NS}	51.72 ^{***}	40.61 ^{***}	23.32 ^{***}
Karnataka	3.88 ^{NS}	3.79 ^{NS}	4.49 ^{NS}	126.58 ^{***}	153.07 ^{***}	38.89 ^{***}

***, ** and * and Significant at 1, 5 and 10 per cent level.

NS: Non-significant.

production (48.70 per cent per annum) and productivity (10.21 per cent per annum) were observed, respectively, in the Bagalkote district. Among the production districts, Bidar registered the highest instability in the area, and with respect to productivity, Bagalkote observed the highest instability in the production of the seedless variety of grapes. All districts in Karnataka registered a positive and significant growth in area and production, among which Bagalkote topped, and Vijayapura was placed last.

Miscellaneous Varieties of Grapes

Miscellaneous grape varieties produced in Karnataka include wine varieties such as cabernet, shiraz, zinfandel and chenin blanc and table varieties such as Cheema Sahebi, Pandari Sahebi, Gulabi, Bhokri, Kali Sahebi, Sonaka and Tas-a-Ganesh (clones of Thompson Seedless). Compared to Bengaluru blue and seedless varieties, the production, area and productivity of miscellaneous varieties are negligible.

The positive CGRs of area (3.88 per cent per annum), production (3.79 per cent per annum) and productivity (4.49 per cent per annum) of miscellaneous varieties of grape were found in Karnataka during 2001-02 to 2018-19 (Table 6). A similar growth rate was found in the study conducted by Kumar and Devaraj (2016). The area (59.77 per cent per annum), production (102.89 per cent per annum) and productivity (26.99 per cent per annum) of miscellaneous varieties of grape increased significantly in the Chikkaballapura district. The area and production of miscellaneous varieties remained more unstable, while productivity remained stable in Karnataka. The district of Bengaluru urban registered the highest negative growth rate in the area, production and productivity of miscellaneous varieties. The lowest instability indices of area (9.18) and production (23.63) indicated its stability

in the Bengaluru rural district. Lower instability of productivity was found in other districts in the state.

CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, growth is necessary for developing the horticulture sector in Karnataka. The area, production and productivity of Anab-e-Shahi, seedless grapes and miscellaneous varieties were significant, with positive growth rates. Instability in area, production and productivity of miscellaneous grapes are very high compared to all other varieties of grapes. The study showed that there was ample opportunity for the expansion of grape cultivation in the state, and therefore, the government needs to develop a proper mechanism for instant availability of credit, interest subvention and insurance to grape producers in the state. The grape growers need to be encouraged to establish a grape producer's organization to benefit small and marginal farmers. Processing infrastructure may be encouraged, which will incentivise farmers to put more acreage under grapes. Public-private partnerships need to be encouraged to manage the production and market-related risks in grape cultivation, allowing a healthy investment environment including infrastructure facilities, information support and maintenance of grades and standards.

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